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Development of the light industry of Uzbekistan and the conditions created for it

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Annotation. *The textile industry occupies a leading position in the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, with sufficient raw materials, qualified personnel, and labor. The development of the light industry, which is Uzbekistan's strategic sector of the economy of our country, the expansion of markets and improving the competitiveness of products is one of the topical issues.*

The textile and light industry occupies an important position in the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan and is at the center of industrial production. This sector produces products for public consumption, which, in turn, ensures a large portion of the market. Additionally, the industry provides a large number of jobs for the country's population, including the employment of women in the industry, which allows them to maintain a demographic balance in industrial areas. One of the most important factors is the growth of export potential. The growth of export potential is directly proportional to the economic potential of the country and the growth of the living standards of the population.

Keywords: *clothing, textile, light industry, export, economy, brand market .*

Uzbekistan currently has a large and diversified textile and light industry network. Its share accounts for 25 percent of industrial output and 13 percent of its production capital. At the same time, 32% of the industrial workers of the republic are working there. Uzbekistan has a rich raw material base (cotton, wool, karakul, silk) for the development and provision of all sectors of the light industry, and also adequate conditions for the rapid development of the economy (natural climatic, territorial and labor resources). The light industry of the Republic is developing at high rates. If in 1991 7% of cotton produced in our country was processed, today it is above 40%.

The development of textile, clothing, and knitting, leather and footwear industries, expanding the range and assortment of finished products, as well as the development of investment and export activities of the light industry of our country is one of the pressing issues.

Taking this into account, the main program for enterprises is the tasks outlined in our President Sh. Mirziyoyev decree of September 16, 2019 "On measures to further develop the light industry and stimulate the production of finished products." The Decree sets the task to achieve international prestige of national brands in the textile and clothing industry, to implement targeted strategies for further development of the fashion industry of the country.

As a result of the reforms carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the growth of the number of enterprises in the light industry is creating a strong competitive environment. In this case, the main challenge facing businesses is to maintain their competitiveness and prevent the risk of being squeezed out of the market in various ways. Ensuring

competitiveness is one of the main objectives of any enterprise.

To further deepen the reforms in the textile and clothing industry, to create favorable conditions for the rapid development and diversification of the sector, several efforts are being made to increase the volume of investments in the deep processing of textile products and export of finished products.

Measures are taken to create more than 80 percent of the country's cotton fiber and more than 45 percent of the yarn produced in the country, as well as the export of finished products in 2018 at \$ 1.6 billion.

Privileges and preferences for the development of leather and footwear and fur industries, as well as the export potential, allowed to increase the production of ready-made leather by 6% and leather production by 44%.

Production of light industry in Uzbekistan is increasing day by day. Production of the light industry in Uzbekistan is increasing day by day. Industrial goods have been produced in the 2014 year 84011.6 billion som, in the 2015 year 97598.2 billion som, in the 2016 year 111869.4 billion som, in the 2017 year 148816.0 billion som, in the 2018 year 235340.7 billion som. Textile goods had been produced in the 2017 year 16,763.3 billion som, in the 2018 year 24835.2 billion som and increased by 113.3% compared to 2017 year. Clothing goods had been produced in the 2017 year 6108.2 billion som, in the 2018 year 7732.2 billion som, it is increased by 104.9% compared to the 2017 year. Leather and related products had been produced in the 2017 year was 1414.6 billion som, in the 2018 year 1647.9 billion som, and it is increased by 102.1% compared to 2017 year.

[18] Table-1

Table-1. Indicators of light industry production for 2014-2018 years

№	Types of products	Measure	2014 y	2015 y	2016 y	2017 y	2018 y
1	Industrial products	billion som	84011,6	97598,2	111869,4	148816,0	235340,7
2	Textile production	billion som	10839,5	13241,7	13335,3	16763,3	24835,2
3	Clothing manufacture	billion som	1308,7	1585,3	4318,5	6108,2	7732,2
4	Production of leather and related products	billion som	527,2	757,9	981,4	1414,6	1647,9

Source: Uzbekitan Department of Statistics information for the end of 2018.

In our country's light industry enterprises are given some privileges:

-enterprises with a share of export of finished sewing and knit products in total gross revenue by the end of the reporting period are exempt from property tax until January 1, 2023;

-the taxable income tax base of textile, sewing, leather, footwear, and fur industries will be reduced by seven years in equal shares for the cost of building modern cleaning, and sewerage facilities;

-organizations that launch modern automated slaughter complexes and leather processing companies are exempt from land tax until January 1, 2023;

-Foreign consultants of "Uztuqimachisanoat" and "Uzcharmsanoat" associations, as well as foreign specialists working in textile, sewing and knitting, leather and fur industries, pay income tax from individuals at the rate of 50% of the established rate.

On the basis of deep processing of raw materials, a target program for the production and export of Textiles, sewing, leather shoes and fur products with high added value has been developed, based on the

requirements of the market, for 2020-2025 years. According to him, textile and sewing-knitted products are planned to produce 4225.5 million USD in 2019 year, 5861.6 million USD in 2020 year, 8058.2 million USD in 2021 year, 11319.3 million USD in 2022 year, 12514.1 million USD in 2023 year, 13764.6 million USD in 2024 year, 3.5 times more than in 2019 by 2025 years. Finished yarn finishing, 471,0 million sq. m in 2019 year location if by 2025 year this indicator increased by 3 times to 1425,9 million sq. The production of ready-made knitted fabrics will increase in 2025 year by 546 thousand tons in comparison with 2019 year in 3,1 times. The production of sewing and knitting products will increase in 2025 year by 3205.3 thousand units in comparison with 2019 year in 4.1 times. And the volume of textiles and sewing and knitting products export is planned to increase by 2025 year to 7075,00 million USD and to 3.3 times more than in 2019 year. It can be seen that the main goal of the production and export development of light industry products has been set in our country. [20]

Table-2

Table-2. In Uzbekistan textile and sewing — the production and export of knitted products is planned for 2020-2025 years

TARGET PARAMETERS

№	Product name	Measure	2019 (pending)	forecasting					
				2020 y.	2021 y.	2022 y.	2023 y.	2024 y.	2025 y
1	Production volume of textile and sewing products	Million USD	4325,5	5861,6	8 058,2	11319,3	12514,1	13764,6	15028,5
2	Threads	thousand tons	623,7	770,3	921,4	930,2	974,3	990,3	1032,5
2.1	<i>Threads of which painted and mixed</i>	<i>thousand tons</i>	<i>182,5</i>	<i>223,6</i>	<i>248,5</i>	<i>276,0</i>	<i>413,0</i>	<i>463,8</i>	<i>470,5</i>
3	Ready yarn, total:	million square meters m.	471,0	963,4	1 061,9	1 237,9	1 253,4	1 364,2	1 425,9
3.1	<i>Ready yarn including ready-made cotton fabrics (mixed, synthetic, wooly, wool-mixed, blanket, decorative furniture, technical, special fabrics)</i>	<i>million square meters m.</i>	<i>130,3</i>	<i>223,6</i>	<i>248,5</i>	<i>276</i>	<i>413,6</i>	<i>463,8</i>	<i>470,5</i>
4	Ready knitwear	thousand tons	174,8	227,5	350,0	406,8	520,0	540,0	546
5	Sewing and knitting products	million units	790	1 070,6	1680	2 850	2248,3	3080,0	3205,3
6	Textile Gallantry	Billion sum	72	106,5	156,8	191,6	221,3	278,1	360,5
7	Socks	million pairs	260,8	312,4	325,9	409,3	415,1	421,8	427
8	Exports of textile and garment products	Million USD	2156,4	2 703,3	3130	3 908,3	4760,00	5 731,9	7075,00

Source: <http://www.lex.uz/docs/4516526>

Table -3. In Uzbekistan the production and export of leather shoes and fur products is planned for 2020-2025 years

TARGET PARAMETERS

№	Product name	Measure	2019 (pending)	Prediction					
				2020 y.	2021 y.	2022 y.	2023 y.	2024 y.	2025 y.
I.	The volume of industrial production	Million USD	349,9	455,9	519,1	660,5	809,1	1116,0	2250,0
1.	Shoes	million pairs	86,1	105,8	154,2	205,3	230,2	258,4	289,7
	<i>including:</i>								
	women's shoes	million pairs	17,2	22,1	35,8	51,1	60,0	77,9	104,8
2.	Leather Clothes	thousand units	18,5	23,5	26,8	35,3	39,5	44,2	49,5
3.	Leather and perfumery products	Million USD	4,8	7,4	8,1	11,2	12,6	14,5	16,4
4.	Leather total:	million square meters dm	1 125,0	1460,0	1 617,5	2179,4	2470,9	2772,0	3148,6
5.	Wool	tonn	2 260,0	2400,0	2880,0	3 500,0	3 920,0	4390,0	4931,8
II.	Exports of leather and footwear and fur products and wool products	Million USD	190,0	230,0	280,0	335,0	520,7	910,7	1500,0

Source: <http://www.lex.uz/docs/4516526>

A targeted program for the production and export of leather and footwear and fur products for 2020 - 2025 has been developed. Production of leather and footwear and fur products will reach \$ 2,250.0 million by 2025, while exports - \$ 1,500.0 million. Out of them, by 2025 it is planned to produce 289.7 million pairs of shoes, 49.5 thousand leather shoes and 16.4 million USDars for leather goods. [20]Table-3

It is well known from the indicators of light industry production in the textile industry of Uzbekistan. As it turns out, the region has a great potential for the development of the textile and garment industry. With this in mind, in to increase the competitiveness of our enterprises both in the domestic and foreign markets, it is necessary to produce products that are in demand in the market.

As a summary, I can say that There are several of problems that are expected to be addressed in this area to bring light industry sectors to higher levels, which can be addressed through the following tasks:

1. It is necessary to develop the textile industry, to create new capacities for the production of ready fabrics, including the production of modern types of products that are in demand in the domestic and world markets.

2. It is necessary to develop the production of inexpensive mixed fibers in the Republic through the production of artificial and synthetic fibers and threads (viscose, acetate, polyester, polyester, polyamide) in the chemical industry.

3. It is necessary to create high-end design products in the garment industry that meet international standards and are in demand in the domestic and foreign markets. In this regard, the Design Center, established as a part of the company, must work to create products that meet the ever-changing fashion needs.

4. It is necessary to hold annual national exhibitions of the textile and fashion industries in the regions and to develop a unified information portal for enterprises. This will allow the light industry to produce products based on the achievements of the modern fashion industry and gain a foothold in local and global markets.

In conclusion, it is important to note that one of the leading sectors of the national economy opens up broad economic and social opportunities for the textile and clothing industry, such as expanding export potential and geography by expanding the production of high-quality raw materials and introducing fashion design services.

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